

success story

> Pilot 3: Infrastructure & Transport Management

Assessing the CC impact of port activity by correlating the cruise and vessel traffic with spatially augmented air quality data of the Baleares islands

Estimating ground-level air pollutant concentrations at higher spatial resolution by fusing Sentinel-5P and in situ data

Ensuring climate change mitigation and maintaining air quality are the foremost environmental concerns that all European ports prioritize. While ports are essential for global economies, they also significantly contribute to atmospheric pollution. Port-city interaction is crucial for regional economic growth in many countries, as ports serve as vital conduits for moving goods and tourists. However, the environmental impact of port activity is a significant concern, particularly for large ports located close to urban areas, such as the Port Authority of Baleares (BPA) in the Balearic Islands, Spain.

Pilot 3 is dedicated to monitoring and prediction of pollution episodes at BPA. It also focuses on the strategic planning and optimization of various port activities, including cargo operations, load/unload operations, cruise ships, and land traffic. To achieve these objectives, real-time data on surface pollution is collected from a network of 25 in-situ stations located across the five port areas. These stations measure surface concentration of air pollutants such as NO₂, O₃, CO, and SO₂ every 10 minutes. However, the current amount of available data is insufficient to construct pollution patterns that can produce reliable historical pollution records or predict anomalies in pollution levels outside the port areas. This is particularly true in nearby cities or regional offshore areas with high vessel traffic, where local and regional variations must be considered, but no in-situ stations are available to collect the necessary data.

Sentinel-5P mission can frequently map most locations on Earth and provide information about the vertical column density of air pollutants, which is a different physical quantity than the surface concentrations measured by ground stations. The spatial distribution of surface concentrations can be estimated by fusing Sentinel-5P and other proxy data such as ERA5 meteorological and GTOPO30 topographic data through training machine learning models with in-situ surface measurements. We demonstrated that the extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) model can generate ground-level concentration maps for various air pollutants (NO₂, O₃, SO₂ and CO) at 1 km spatial resolution by utilizing hourly concentration measurements (07/2022-05/2023) acquired by more than 3300 stations and available through the European Environmental Agency's Air Quality e-Reporting database. The model can infer ground-level concentrations at arbitrary locations where no in-situ monitoring stations are available and can capture up to 61% of NO₂ variation with a mean absolute error of 3.6 µg/m³. The high spatial resolution ground-level concentrations were used to support the monitoring of atmospheric emissions produced by the vessel traffic and detection of pollution events in the Freus area (route between Eivissa and la Savina ports).

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